

Reduplication of Balinese and Japanese Verbs: A Contrastive Analysis

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Abstract

The focus of this research is on the process of verb morphosis that undergoes duplication as well as its meaning in Balinese. The method in this study is a descriptive method. In this study, reverbs were generated from the Balinese language either due to the process of full decimation or duplication with phoneme changes. While in Japanese reverbs are produced with three processes, namely perfect repetition, partial repetition, and repetition of changing sounds. In Japanese, re-verbs are produced with three processes: perfect repetition has the meaning of expressing repetition/ continuity. The second process is by partial repetition which has the meaning of expressing emphasis. Furthermore, the third is the repetition of changing sounds or repetitions involving vocal changes and consonant changes that have a meaning expressing similarity to one of the elements.

1. Introduction

Linguistics consists of several branches of science. One of them is morphology. Morphology is a branch of linguistics that studies the structure and formation of words. The process of word formation is called the morphic process or morphological process. The morphic process is the way a word is formed by connecting one morpheme with another morpheme (Muchtar, 2006: 34). This study analyzed starting from the basic word of a verb. The basic word is a combination of morphemes that language considers to be the smallest unit that can be agreed upon as a free form. From the basic word then done formation with a forming tool that is a reduplication. After knowing the type of reduplication then will be found grammatical meaning. Grammatical meaning is a meaning that arises as a result of grammatical processes such as affixation, reduplication, and composition. Grammatical meaning depends on the accompanying context. This study peeled the grammatical meaning of the morphine process of verbs replicated in Balinese and Japanese.

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This study discussed the morphemes process of verbs replicating in Balinese and Japanese. Followed by describing the grammatical meaning and the result of the formation of the morphemes process of the pattern of reduplication of verb structures in Balinese and Japanese.

In Balinese there is a verb *kecog* meaning in Indonesian is 'jump'. The verb can be replicated into two types, namely *kecog-kecog* which is replicated without any changes in phonemes and without affixation. The second reduplication is *kecag-kecog*. In this reduplication, the basic word undergoes a phoneme change by being marked by a change in vowels. On the whole, multiplication produced a meaning that expresses reduplication or continuity which is the meaning of showing something repeatedly and continuously. While verb reduplication with phoneme changes expresses the meaning of reduplication of activities without increasing the intensity of the activity.

This study also discusses the multiplication of verbs in Japanese. The reduplication in Japanese verbs is known as 'Jougo Doushi'. Jougo Doushi has three types of morphic processes: 嶮菟錡 'kanzen jougo' is a form of perfect reduplication or reduplication of the entire basic form without phoneme changes or impositions. For example: *yasumiyasumi* which means 'take a rest'. While 薙錡 'bubun jougo' is a form of partial reduplication. For example, *susuru* which means 'inhaling'. In the process of replicating some words in Japanese, there is also the phenomenon of verb reduplication with the addition of affixation. For example: *narenareshii* is 'familiar'. The next form of reduplication referred to as 誓蠡錡 'onkoutai jougo' is a reduplication accompanied by a change in sound or reduplication with vocal changes and consonant changes. For example, *kawarugawaru* which means 'over and over again'. In the all multiplication produced meaning expresses reduplication / continuity which is a meaning that indicates something repetitive and continuous.

This is an attraction in this study. In addition to discussing the multiplication of verbs, it will also be searched for meaning and results of its formation. And at the end of each discussion will be given a comparison between Balinese and Japanese. All these discussions are summarized in a study entitled. " Contrastive Analysis: Reduplication of Balinese and Japanese Verbs".

This research is expected to increase the understanding and knowledge of readers about morphological studies in both Balinese and Japanese. And to provide input to language observers about the uniqueness between two different language groups, especially in the field of linguistics. After this research, it is expected that there will be many studies involving two languages or better still in the same or different language groups to get the uniqueness of each language.

2. Literature Review

Previous research related to this study includes Bawa (1981) with the title 'Balinese Language Structure'. In this study, three types of Balinese reduplication patterns were found, including whole reduplication, complete reduplication with vocal variations, and partial reduplication, as well as the presence of affixation which includes prefixes, confections, and suffixes. Temaja (2018) in an article entitled "Balinese Language Reduplication Patterns: Comparisons with The Pattern of Reduplication of Austronesian Languages". Bawa and Temaja research there are similar to this study in terms of discussion about the pattern of reduplication of word structure in Balinese only this study also adds the grammatical meaning and the results of the formation of the morphemes process.

The reduplication of Japanese is also found in previous studies. Daulay (2009) with the thesis title "Analysis On In Koutai Japanese Reviewed In Terms of Morphophonemic". In this study, morphological processes and morphophonemic processes were reviewed in Japanese. Sofiani (2017) in her thesis entitled "The Structure and Meaning of Japanese Reduplication". This study discussed the formation of the word multiplication in Japanese along with the meaning derived from the word multiplication. The difference between the two previous studies is that there has not been an in-depth study of verb reduplication in Japanese. In addition, it has not been studied regarding the results of verb

reduplication. The most difference is that there has been no research comparing the morphemes process of verb reduplication between Balinese and Japanese.

3. Methods, Concepts, and Theories

In the process of analysis, methods are needed as procedures and concepts and theories as guidelines. The following is described the methods, concepts, and theories used in this research.

3.1 Research Methods and Techniques

Methods and techniques are two important things in a study. The method is a way of approaching, observing, analyzing, and explaining a phenomenon (Kridalaksana: 2011). While engineering is a way to carry out the method (Sudaryanto: 2015). The following three stages are the stages that researchers do to get the final results of the data. The three stages are the stages of data collection, the stages of analyzing data, and the presentation of data analysis results.

In the data collection stage, this tapping technique is used followed by advanced techniques in the form of record-making techniques and ability-free listening techniques. The technique of recording is to record things that are considered important. The stage of data analysis is a very decisive stage. At this stage, the data that has been obtained will be analyzed. The method used to analyze data is a descriptive method. A descriptive method of analysis is a research method conducted based on existing linguistic facts, namely by describing, focusing on a problem, and presenting based on existing data (Sudaryanto: 2015). Descriptive methods are used to tabulate data, classify data, and describe matters related to this research.

The presentation stage is the effort of the researcher to display in the form of a written "report" things that have been produced from the work of analysis, especially the rules (Sudaryanto; 2015). The way the rules are presented is known as the method of presenting the rules; It consists of two types, namely informal and formal. The informal presentation method is the formulation with ordinary words (a natural language) while the formal presentation is the formulation with signs and symbols (an artificial language) (Sudaryanto: 2015). In this study, the results of data analysis are presented using informal methods, namely explaining the data by discussing all elements descriptively.

3.2. Concepts

In each study, the concept is needed as a reference and the basis for mapping the type of research. Concepts consist of understanding related to an object. The concept is created by classifying or grouping certain objects that share the same characteristics (Umar, 2004, p. 51). This study was studied in the field of linguistics in the field of morphology. (Crystal, 1987, p. 82) in *The Cambridge Encyclopedia of Language*, states that "Morphology: the branch of grammar studies the structure of words." Morphology: a branch of grammar that studies the structure of words. Morphology is also called the science of language that studies the ins and outs of word-formation. While (Verhaar, 2008) argues that morphology is a field of linguistics that studies the arrangement of word parts grammatically. Similar thoughts were also put forward by (Kridalaksana, 2011) who stated that morphology, which is the field of linguistics that studies morphemes and their combinations; is a part of the language structure that includes words and parts of words, i.e. morphemes. In addition, morphology has also studied the process of word-formation itself. Based on the opinions of experts, morphology is a lingual field that learns about the ins and outs of the word and the process of its formation.

3.3. Theories

In this research, there needs to be an understanding of some of the theories that will be used in the analysis process. The guidelines used in analyzing the data in this study are the morphemic process of verbs in both Balinese and Japanese. The morphic process involves components (1) of the basic form, (2) the forming tools (affixation, reduplication, composition, acronymization, and conversion), (3) grammatical meanings, and (4) the results of the formation process (Chaer, 2002, p. 25). This study focused on the basic forms of verbs in Balinese and Japanese with a forming tool, namely duplication. This study will also be revealed grammatical meaning due to the morphic process and the results of its formation.

3.3.1. Basic Words

The basic word is an element of a language spoken or written that is the embodiment of the unity of feelings and thoughts that can be used in language. The base word is a combination of morphemes that linguists consider to be the smallest unit that can be taught as a free form. A basic word is a stand-alone unit of language, consisting of a single morpheme or a combined morpheme. The function of the basic word is as a support for the meaning and usefulness of the affix including grammatical functions.

3.3.2. Definition of Reduplication

Samsuri (1982, p. 191) argues that reduplication as a morphological process is widely found in the languages of the world. Reduplication is a mortician process that repeats the basic or partial form of the basic form (Verhaar, 2008, p. 152). (Matthews, 1978:, p.127) also agrees that a duplication is a form of iteration that is not only whole but can also be partial. From the two definitions, it can be concluded that reduplication is a morphic process by repeating the basic form as a whole or it can also be partial or partial. Reduplication according to (Ramlan, 2012, p. 62) is divided into four groups, namely: All reduplication: reduplication of all basic morphemes, without changes in phonemes and not combining with the process of setting up the affix. Partial reduplication is a partial duplication of the base morpheme, e.g. first being first of all.

Reduplication that combines with the process of establishing affix is a reduplication that occurs together and also supports one function. Reduplication with changes in phonemes, such as motion into motion, all-rounder into sundries. Latupeirissa (2016) added about reduplication, namely the reduplication of grammatical unit forms, both in whole and in part, either accompanied by phoneme variations or not. Reduplication is a morphic process that repeats the basic word, both in whole, in part, and with changes in sound (Chaer, 2003, p. 182). There are several kinds of reduplications, namely: 1. Full reword, which is obtained by repeating all basic forms, can be divided into three, among others: Dwilingga, namely: a reword whose basic form is a free morpheme. Dwipurwa, namely: a reword whose basic form is the word affix. Dwilingga copy sound is a dwilingga that undergoes a change in sound. 2. The reword is added, for example: berjalan-jalan, tulis-menulis, kekanak-kanakan, dan lain-lain. 3. Pseudo-rewording. This form is actually a basic word, so it is not the result of reduplication. Examples: laba-laba, ubur-ubur, undur-undur, kupu-kupu, dan empek-empek.

Reduplikasi in Japanese is known as Juufuku (重複). (Koizumi, 1993, p. 108-109) states that reduplication in Japanese is divided into 2, including 1. 枋貢 gokan no juufuku: a reword of its basic form. 2. 枋貢膏籬 gokan no juufuku to setsuji: a re-word undergoing an affixation process. (Koizumi, 1993, p. 108), divided juufuku into 2 among others 1. Gitaigo is a language sound that is expressed such as the state of its object or the sound of language that arises by looking at the state of the object. 2. Giongo is a language or sound that resembles the sound of objects or animals. Both are anomalies or sound imitations. Similar opinions were also expressed by (Oosato, 2013, p. 1) who stated that

reduplication is a word formed from the reduplication of word elements. In contrast to (Oosato, Akimoto, 2002, p. 91) states that duplication is a word that is a merger of the same word basis.

(Koizumi, 1993, p. 108) mentions the reduplication of the Japanese language with juufuku, but (Akimoto, 2002, p. 91) calls reduplication with jougo. In general, jougo is divided into 3, namely: a. 嶮菟蹄 'kanzen jougo' is a perfect reduplication or reduplication of the entire basic form without phoneme changes or abuses. b. 薙蹄 'bubun jougo' or partial reduplication. For example: 'inhale'. c. 誓蠡蹄 'onkoutai jougo' or reduplication by sound changes or reduplications involving vocal changes and consonant changes. The Japanese Wikipedia divided jougo by word class, including:

Jougo meishi-daimeishi (noun and pronominal), Jougo meishi-daimeishi rendaku (noun and pronominal re-enactment with sound changes), Jougo doushi (re-verb), Jougo doushi' 'bubunjougo' (partial reduplicate verb), Jougo keiyoushi (re-adjective), Jougo fukushi (reword adverb), Jougo giongo.gitaigo (imitation sound of re-anomatope), Jougo gairaigo (reduplication of foreign words), and Jougo shuujougo (reword collection).

3.3.3. *The Meaning of Reduplication*

Words that undergo reduplication will change their meaning. (Oosato, 2013, p. 3) describes the meaning of reduplication into 10 types of meanings among others. Plural meaning, Action reduplication meaning, Emphasis meaning, Scattered depiction meaning, Space meaning, Continuity or continuous meaning, Reduction meaning, Minimum meaning, Past meaning, and Meaning of adjective markers.

The meaning of reduplication in Japanese can be divided into three types including the plural meaning, the meaning of emphasis, and the meaning of continuity (Oosato, 2013, p.12). Similarly, (Ishikawa, 2017, p.7) divides the meaning of reduplication in Japanese into three, among others.

1. Plural

A meaning that indicates more than one. Example: 人々 hitobito "people".

2. Reduplication

A meaning that expresses duplication, habit, continuity, and frequency of occurrence of things. Example: 度々 tabitabi "often".

3. Emphasis

Meaning that expresses the emphasis of the degree of a word to emphasize or accentuate the meaning of the word. Example: 近々 chikajika "immediately".

(Sunarni, Johana, 2010, p. 42-45) state that reduplication in Japanese has 8 meanings, namely as follows.

1. The reduplication of the nomina indicates the plural.
2. Reduplication with the structure of repeating verbs means performing two activities at a time that are simultaneously or equal to the forms of -nagara "sambal" and -shitsutsu "continuously".
3. The reduplication of the base of the adjective expresses the meaning of reinforcing the repeated word.
4. The reduplication of adverbs gives meaning to strengthen the repeated word.
5. The reduplication of interjection gives meaning to reinforce the repeated word.
6. The reduplication of irregular phrases, according to their constituent words.
7. Reduplication of synonymous elements according to the word meaning of one of its constituent elements.
8. Reduplication on the reduplication of the antonymous element the meaning is opposite to each other according to the word of the two constituent elements.

Meanwhile, (Taume, 2014, p.78) states that the meaning of a reword that undergoes the addition of the suffix /~shii/, then its meaning will be related to the meaning of the base word. Reword meanings that undergo the addition of the suffix /~shii/ indicate the same nuances or feelings that arise as the base word so that the result and the meaning in the base word have an indirect connection. The meaning of duplication in Japanese has 6 meanings, namely:

1. Expressing plural is a meaning that expresses something many or more than one.
2. Expressing emphasis is a meaning that indicates the existence of more emphasis or to emphasize and accentuate the meaning of a word.
3. Expresses duplication/continuity i.e. a meaning that indicates something repetitive and persistent.
4. Expresses an indirect connection with the root word.
5. Expresses a resemblance to one of the elements, that is, the meaning of duplication similar to the meaning of one of the elements of the basic word.
6. Declaring reciprocal, is the meaning of duplication expressing mutual or contradictory nature. This can be seen from the basic word.

3.3.2. Results of the Forming Process

The morphological process in this case is a process of word-formation that can produce grammatical forms and meanings. The two things have a close relationship. The form is the physical form while the grammatical meaning is the content of the form. The physical form of the pasting process is the word interpretation or also known as the word affixation, a derivative word, or also the word publication. The physical form of the duplication process is rewording or known as reshaping. The physical form of the composition process is a merged word or combination of words, groups of words or also called compound word terms (about compound word terms cause many problems) (Chaer, 2002, p. 28-29).

4. Results and Discussion

The morphological process in this case is a process of word-formation that can produce grammatical forms and meanings. The two things have a close relationship. The form is the physical form while the grammatical meaning is the content of the form. The physical form of the pasting process is the word interpretation or also known as the word affixation, a derivative word, or also the word publication. The physical form of the duplication process is rewording or known as reshaping. The physical form of the composition process is a merged word or combination of words, groups of words or also called compound word terms (about compound word terms cause many problems) (Chaer, 2002, p. 28-29).

In the data analysis stage, a compendium is described related to the morphemic process. Morphemic processes include basic forms, forming devices (consisting of affixation, duplication, composition, acronymization, and conversion), grammatical meaning, and the result of the formation process (Chaer, 2002, p.25). This study focused on the basic forms of verbs in Balinese and Japanese with a forming tool, namely duplication. In this study, the grammatical meaning of the morphemic process will be revealed and the results of the formation. Here is an explanation for each of these components.

1. Basic Forms

The basic word is an element of language that is spoken or written down, it is the embodiment of the unity of feelings and thoughts that can be used in language. The base word consists of a combination

of morphemes that are considered the smallest units that can be taught as a free form. A base word is a unit of language that can stand alone. It consists of a single morpheme or a combined morpheme. The root word serves as a support for the meaning and usefulness of affixes including grammatical functions. Examples of basic words from the duplication of Balinese verbs are *tolih* (from the word *tolahtolih*), *kipek* (from the word *kipakkipek*), and others. While examples of basic words from the duplication of Japanese verbs are *yasumi* (from the word *yasumiyasumi*), *kaesu* (from the word *kaesukaesu*), etc.

2. Forming Tools

From the basic word, then the formation is carried out with a forming tool, namely duplication. (Samsuri, 1982, p. 91) argues that duplication is a morphological process found in many languages of the world. Duplication is a morphemic process that repeats a basic shape or part of that basic form (Verhaar, 2008, p. 152). (Matthews, 1978, p.127) also agrees that a duplication is a form of iteration that is not only whole but can also be partial. From these two definitions, it can be concluded that duplication is a morphemic process by repeating the basic form as a whole or it can also be partial or partial. (Ramlan, 2012, p. 62) divides duplication into four types including the whole duplication: duplication of all basic morphemes, without phoneme changes and not combining with the affixing process, for example, *sepeda-sepeda* (bicycles). Partial duplication is a partial duplication of its basic morphemes, the first example being first of all. Duplication by the process of affixing is the duplication of occupying one function, for example, "*anak*" becomes "*anak-anak*", and "*hitam*" becomes "*hitam-hitam*". Duplication with the change of phonemes, for example, motion into gestures, "*serba*" becomes "*serba-serbi*".

This study focused on duplicating all Balinese and Japanese language verbs. In Balinese, there are two processes of verb duplication.

1. *Dwilingga* is a form of duplication of the entire basic morpheme without changes in phonemes and not joining the process of affixation, for example:

- *tolih* + *tolih* = *tolih-tolih*
'see' + 'see' = 'look around'
- *dengok* + *dengok* = *dengok-dengok*
'take a look' + 'take a look' = 'looking around'
- *kecog* + *kecog* = *kecog-kecog*
'jump' + 'jump' = 'jumping up and down'
- *kletok* + *kletok* = *kletok-kletok*
'knock' + 'knock' = 'pegging'
- *gliling* + *gliling* = *gliling-gliling*
'rolling' + 'rolling' = 'rolling around'
- *tundik* + *tundik* = *tundik-tundik*
'poke' + 'poke' = 'poke'

From the example data, the base word changed verbs in Balinese undergoing duplication without any change in phonemes and without affixation.

2. *Dwilingga salin suara* is a form of verb duplication with phoneme changes in Balinese. For example:

- *tolih* becomes *tolah-tolih*
'see' becomes 'look around'
- *jongkok* becomes *jangkak-jongkok*
'jongkok' becomes 'squats'
- *kipek* becomes *kipak kipek*

- ‘turned’ becomes ‘turning’
- tundik becomes tundak-tundik
- ‘poke’ becomes ‘poke’

In this duplication, the base word undergoes a change in phonemes by characterizing the change of the last vowel letter in each base word to the vocal letter "a" in the results of the duplication. In addition, the results of its duplication precede the base word. In Japanese, there are three types of verb duplication processes. Here's an example.

1. 嶮菟蹄 ‘kanzen jougo’ (perfect duplication or duplication of the entire base shape without phoneme changes or fixations). Examples:

- 走る+走る = 走る走る

hashiru + hashiru = hashiru-hashiru

‘run’ + ‘run’ = ‘running around’

2. 部分蹄 ‘bubunjougo’ (verba ulang dengan reduplikasi sebagian).

In the process of duplicating some words in Japanese, there is also the phenomenon of verb duplication with the addition of affixation. Examples:

- 慣れる + 慣れる = 慣れしい

nareru + nareru = nareshii

‘get used to’ + ‘get used to’ = ‘accustomed’.

3. 誓蠡蹄 ‘onkoutai jougo’ (Duplication involving voice changes or duplication involving vowel changes and consonant changes). Examples:

- 代わる+代わる = 代わる代わる

kawaru + kawaru = kawarugawaru

‘replace’ + ‘replace’ = ‘alternately’.

- 返す+返す = 返す返す

kaesu + kaesu = kaesugaesu

‘return’ + ‘return’ = ‘repeatedly’

3. Grammatical Meaning

Grammatical meanings are meanings that arise as a result of grammatical processes such as affixation, reduplication, and composition. The grammatical meaning depends on the context associated with it. In this study, the grammatical meaning of the morphemic process of reduplicating verbs in Balinese and Japanese was discussed.

In Balinese, verbs that undergo complete duplication are produced by the meaning of the increase in the intensity of activities, for example, *tolih-tolih* ‘look around’. The data shows continuous ‘seeing’ activities carried out. Meanwhile, verb reduplication with phoneme changes has the meaning of reduplicating activities without increasing the intensity of the activity. For example, *tundak-tundik* which means ‘touching’. The reduplicated word has the meaning of ‘touching’ then stopping and repeating ‘touching back’.

In Japanese, perfect reduplication or reduplication of all basic forms without phoneme change or abuse has the meaning of reduplication/continuity expression which is a meaning that indicates something repetitive and persistent. While duplication with partial repetition has the meaning of expressing affirmation, a meaning that indicates further emphasis or to emphasize and highlight the meaning of the word. In addition, sound re-reduplication or repetition involving sound changes and static changes has the meaning of expressing similarities with elements, that is, the meaning of repetition, which is similar to that contained in its basic word elements.

4. The Results of the Forming Process

The morphological process or process of word-formation has two results, namely grammatical form and meaning, that is, two closely related things; form is its physical form and grammatical meaning is the content of that physical form or form (Chaer, 2002, p.28). The physical form of the process of pasting is a word with affixation, also called an affixation word, a derivative word, or a published word. The physical form of the reduplication process is rewording or also called reshape. The physical form of the composition process is the word merge, also called a combination of words, groups of words, or compound words (about the term the word compounding causes many problems) (Chaer, 2002, p. 28-29).

In this study, re-verbs from the Balinese language were produced both due to the process of full reduplication for example *tolih-tolih* 'look around' and the change of phonemes for example *tundak-tundik* which means 'touching'.

Meanwhile, in Japanese, re-verbs are produced with three processes, namely perfect reduplication for example *走る+走る=走る走る* (*hashiru + hashiru = hashiru-hashiru*), partial reduplication for example *慣れる + 慣れる = 慣れしい* (*nareru + nareru = nareshii*), and sound-changing reduplication for example *代わる+代わる=代わる代わる* (*kawaru + kawaru = kawarugawaru*)

5. Conclusion

This study focuses on the morphemic processes of basic verbs being repeated, as well as their meanings in Balinese and Japanese. The method used in this study is the descriptive method. Descriptive methods are used to tabulate data, classify data, and describe matters related to this study. This study focused on the basic form of verbs in Balinese with the formation of tools, namely duplication and revealing grammatical meanings due to morphemic processes and the results of their formation. From the basic word, it is then formed with a forming tool, namely reduplication. This study focuses on the entire reduction of verbs in Balinese: the redistribution of all basic morphemes, without changes in basic phonemes and not combining with the process of affix formation, and also studies the redistribution of verbs with changes in phonemes in Balinese.

In the process of reduplication, the meaning of the intensity of activity is generated. Whereas the reduction of verbs with a change of phonemes has the meaning of redistributing activity without increasing the intensity of activity. In this study, reworked words were generated from the Balinese language as a result of a process of full reduplication and reduplication with phoneme changes. Whereas in Japanese the reduplication of words is produced by three processes, namely perfect reduplication, partial reduplication, and duplication with voice change. In Japanese, verb duplication with three processes, that is, replication with a perfect change of the entire basic form without a change in phonemes or having the meaning of expressing reduplication or continuity is a meaning that indicates something repetitive. The second process is partial reduplication which has the meaning of expressing emphasis, which is a meaning that indicates the presence of more emphasis or affirms and accentuates the meaning of the word. Furthermore, the third is a reduplication of changing sounds or reduplication involving changes in vowels and changes in consonants. This reduplication has the meaning of expressing a resemblance to one of the elements in other words the meaning of the reduplication is similar to the meaning in one of the elements of the base word.

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